

Main problems with cultural diversity and its solutions

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Annotation: The following article provides teachers with reasons of cultural diversity and proven ways to encourage it in schools.

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If we start the topic of cultural diversity then it is surely be about different types of people from different backgrounds. Most people still confuse what cultural diversity consists. So, let's nail down what cultural diversity is. As each pupil is unique, educators' aim to bring them together should be started from learning each student's background which helps to identify them quickly.

First thing that makes one student different from the other is race. A person skin colour may have negative impact on some students' attitude if it is not treated from early years. It may have a huge impact on how a person is engaging in the classroom. In order to eliminate quarrels between students mentors should teach them to be equal to each other and behave well. However, it takes much time and effort for teachers to create that kind of environment.

Another one is ethnicity which is about an individual's culture and nationality. Most people often get confused about race and ethnicity. People may come from the same race but they might relate to different culture, that's why there are totally different things. For example, two black people may be alike in terms of skin colour but one can come from Africa while the other way from Arabia.

It is essential to note that people have the choice to choose which religion to follow. Force to follow religion is prohibited as it is only a person's preference. There can be a mix of religious beliefs in a classroom which ought to be respected by all. As long as I'm concerned religion should not be the barrier for students to interact, share ideas and become as one big family. On the other side, it should bring all students together.

Language is the next one that mostly prevents students to get closer. It is true that people who interact in the same language understand each other better even without moving your tongue. Nevertheless, teachers are to help them socialise with each other in one language respecting their own ones.

Another reason lies in socio-economic state of students which often leads to bullying or isolation. The reason behind is that some students cannot afford devices like laptop that is required in classroom participation. That's why considering a students' socio-economic status helps to know the condition of a student and try to support him or her financially. Sexual orientation and gender identity are the next ones that students ought to be recognised by others. It is quite essential to make this known to others so that they know how to refer to them.

Fostering inclusion and multicultural education would be quite necessary in the future of a child making it easy to build relationship no matter which gender, race or background he or she has. Both individuals from various culture will not take it seriously and refer to each other politely despite some cultural differences. But how is it achieved?

There are several ways teachers can ensure that students in a classroom are respectful of one's cultural particularities. The dominant action to take is to get to know students very well. Making sure that the teacher is learning every student individually, discovering their interests, hobbies making them feel special and valued. If students feel comfortable with a teacher there is a better chance for establishing strong connections with peers as well. Therefore, interaction with people helps you gain trust and become closer to a person. It is considered that communication is the main key to a successful and strong relationship both with a teacher and peers.

It is also important for teachers to celebrate all students' cultural holidays so pupils get used to mark those cultural holiday parties making the group unite. The person who the holiday belongs will also start to feel pleasant and safe among other students

with different cultural diversity. This teaches not to be selfish and to respect not only yours but other's culture as well.

Last but not least, incorporating diversity in the lesson plan is a great idea to make students feel safe with each other. Assignment for students to prepare presentation about their own culture can be a great idea to introduce themselves as a representative of this culture contributing to enhancement of their knowledge about other people's traditions. Once they are familiar with other cultural peculiarities they will not experience difficulties in the future dealing or working with people from a variety of backgrounds which would be the biggest advantage that makes you an extraordinary individual that may even lead to career prospects.

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